

ON ORGANO-ARSENICAL COMPOUNDS. PART I.

BY D. N. CHATTERJEE AND T. N. GHOSH

For enhanced therapeutic activity against trypanosomes, *p*-amidinoacetylamino-phenylarsonic acid has now been synthesised.

It is known that trypanosomes which have become resistant to one group of arsenical compounds may yet remain sensitive to another. Ehrlich (*Z. angew. Chem.*, 1910, **23**, 2) showed many years ago that a number of arsenobenzene derivatives, of which arseno-phenylglycine is a type, is capable of curing arsenic-resistant infections. These derivatives are all characterised by the presence in their make-up of the acetic acid radical, $-(\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CO}_2\text{H})$. In this connection it should be mentioned that the simple compound, arseno-acetic acid, has very little action on parasites.

Amongst the derivatives of *p*-aminophenylarsonic acid, so far prepared and tested, tryparsamide has been found very effective against trypanosomes. It is, however, interesting to observe that though the phenylglycine analogue of phenylarsonic acid is of comparatively slight value as a trypanocide, the corresponding amide or rather its sodium salt (tryparsamide) is highly effective in certain forms of trypanosomiasis (*Tr. gambiense*, African sleeping sickness and *mal de caderas*) (cf. Pearce and Brown, *J. Exp. Med.*, 1921, **34**, 1). The question naturally arises as to whether the groupings, $\text{CH}_2\text{-COOH}$ in the case of arsenobenzene compounds and $\text{CH}_2\text{-CONH-}$ in the case of phenylarsonic acid compounds, have any special significance in connection with the activity of trypanocidal substances. Further research is, however, needed before any definite relationship can be established.

King, Lourie and Yorke (*Lancet*, 1937, **233**, 136) have found that some symmetrical diamidinoalkanes exhibit pronounced trypanocidal action. In recent years a large number of aromatic diamidines has been synthesised by Ashley, Barber, Ewins, Newbery and Self (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 103), some of which have been found to possess pronounced trypanocidal activity and are found to cure early cases of sleeping sickness in a fortnight or less and act on the naturally arsenic-resistant *T. rhodesiense* in human being. These observations have opened up a new line of research along which important therapeutic substances may be discovered.

In search for a drug which may prove lethal to "arsenic-fast" trypanosomes and also effective in late cases, it has been considered desirable to prepare compounds which will embrace the above features—namely, derivatives of *p*-aminophenylarsonic acid containing the groupings, $\text{CH}_2\text{-CONH-}$ and an amidino group. With this idea in view, *p*-arsanilic acid has now been condensed with ethyl cyanoacetate at $165\text{-}70^\circ$ to yield the compound (I). This cyano derivative reacts with hydrogen sulphide at 0° to give the thioamide (II). It was expected that hydrogen sulphide might also reduce the arsonic acid group to arsenious sulphide (compare German Patent, 205617), but as the compound isolated is soluble in aqueous alkali and ammonia and as its analyses conform

to the structure (II), the possibility of any reduction having taken place is precluded. Moreover, in keeping with the structure (II), the compound is desulphurised by yellow oxide of mercury (*cf.* Guha, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, **44**, 1502).

The compound (I) has now yielded the desired amidine derivative (III) *via* the corresponding imino-ether hydrochloride. The compound (III), which is a derivative of *p*-aminophenylarsonic acid, contains both the amidino and $\text{CH}_2\text{-CONH-}$ groupings.

EXPERIMENTAL

Condensation of Ethyl Cyanoacetate with p-Arsanilic Acid

Formation of *p*-Cyanoacetylaminophenylarsonic Acid (I).—Well powdered *para*-arsanilic acid (50 g.) and ethyl cyanoacetate (50 g.) were thoroughly mixed together and heated under reflux in an oil-bath at 165-70° for 8 hours. The mixture became viscous after 2 hours' heating and then gradually turned into a dark grey mobile liquid. Some amount of ammonia was evolved due to decomposition of excess of ethyl cyanoacetate.

Next day the thick pasty mass was triturated with 10% sodium hydroxide solution, filtered and the filtrate acidified, under cooling, with excess of concentrated hydrochloric acid, when a brown gelatinous precipitate was obtained. The solid was filtered, thoroughly washed with dilute hydrochloric acid and then with water. It is insoluble in hot water and in ordinary organic solvents. It was purified by dissolving in aqueous sodium bicarbonate and treating with charcoal. After standing for about 1 hour, the solution was filtered and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The brown gelatinous mass was filtered, washed thoroughly with water and dried in a vacuum desiccator, when it turned granular and assumed a slightly deeper tinge, yield 12 g. It does not melt even at 300°. (Found: N, 9.42; As, 25.81. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_9\text{O}_4\text{N}_2\text{As}$ requires N, 9.86; As, 26.38 per cent).

The above condensation does not at all take place below 150° and takes place to a very small extent between 150° and 160°, the maximum yield of the condensation product having been obtained by heating the ingredients at 165-70°.

***p*-Thioamidoacetylaminophenylarsonic Acid (II).**—The above compound (I, 8 g.) was dissolved in just the requisite quantity of aqueous sodium bicarbonate and the solution after being cooled to 0° was saturated with sulphuretted hydrogen gas. The solution was then kept in the refrigerator overnight in a well-stoppered flask.

Next day the solution was filtered and acidified, under cooling, with dilute hydrochloric acid, when a brown solid was precipitated. It was dried and washed thoroughly with carbon disulphide. It is insoluble in hot water and in ordinary organic solvents. It was purified by solution in aqueous ammonia and by precipitation with dilute hydrochloric acid, yield 5 g. It does not melt even at 300°. (Found: N, 9.28; S, 10.48; As, 22.92. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_9\text{O}_4\text{N}_2\text{SAs}$ requires N, 8.80; S, 10.06; As, 23.56 per cent).

The aqueous solution of the sodium salt is easily desulphurised by yellow oxide of mercury and gives immediately an insoluble precipitate with mercuric chloride. The aqueous solution of the sodium derivative of the compound (I), however, does not give any precipitate with mercuric chloride.

p-Amidinoacetylaminophenylarsonic Acid (III).—A suspension of a finely powdered sample of the above compound (I, 6 g.) in dry ether (20 c.c.) was treated with absolute alcohol (3.5 c.c.), and the mixture was saturated with dry hydrochloric acid gas at 0°. The mixture was then kept in the refrigerator in a well-stoppered flask for 6 days with occasional, mild shaking. The solid (the corresponding imino-ether hydrochloride) was filtered, washed with dry ether and dried in a vacuum desiccator. The filtrate, when kept in the refrigerator for 6 days more, deposited a further quantity of the imino-ether hydrochloride, the total yield amounting to 5.5 g.

The dry imino-ether hydrochloride (5.5 g.) was finely powdered and treated with alcoholic ammonia (15%, 5c.c.) and kept in a well-stoppered flask in the refrigerator for 5 days with occasional, mild shaking. The solid (the corresponding amidine hydrochloride) was filtered and dried in a vacuum desiccator. It was then triturated with very dilute hydrochloric acid and the solution, after filtration to remove slight impurity, was carefully treated, under cooling, with dilute ammonium hydroxide, when a pale green voluminous precipitate of the free amidine began to separate. The addition of dilute ammonium hydroxide was continued till maximum precipitation was obtained and the solution just turned green. The solid (3 g.) was purified by solution in dilute hydrochloric acid and precipitation, as above, by dilute ammonium hydroxide. The amidine base (III), thus obtained, is a light green powder when dried and does not melt even at 300°. (Found : N, 13.52 ; As, 25.61. $C_6H_{12}O_4N_3As$ requires N, 13.95 ; As, 24.89 per cent). It is readily soluble in aqueous sodium bicarbonate and in dilute ammonium hydroxide and also readily soluble in dilute mineral acids. It is insoluble in hot water and in ordinary organic solvents except glacial acetic acid in which it is sparingly soluble. It could not be, however, crystallised from glacial acetic acid.